

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Instructional leadership, teachers' participation and k to 12 curriculum: Impact on pupils' learning outcomes

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Abstract

The study looked into the relationship of Instructional Leadership, Teachers' Participation, and the K to 12 curriculum on pupils' learning outcomes. It utilized a sequential explanatory research design where questionnaires and interviews are the instruments used to gather necessary data. There were 422 respondents of the study that involved the principals, teachers, and pupils from randomly selected central elementary schools in the four EDDIS of division of Bulacan. Results of the study revealed that the principals always perform their roles as instructional leaders in the school. They give proper technical assistance to their teachers to help the teachers enhance their teaching skills. Teachers' Participation was found to be at high extent as the respondents have given the highest mean responses that fall under the highest verbal description of always. In terms of the K to 12 curriculum, perceived problems were found to have the least mean rating where the respondents have moderately agreed and disagreed. No significant differences were found on the perception of the respondents in terms of Teachers' participation and K to 12 curriculum. On the other hand, significant differences existed in their perceptions of Instructional leadership. In terms of the correlation analysis, Instructional Leadership and Teachers' Participation were significantly correlated on pupils learning outcomes while K to 12 curriculum has no significant relationship on pupils' learning outcomes.

Keywords: Instructional Leadership; Teachers' Participation; K to 12 Curriculum; Pupils' Learning Outcomes

1. Introduction

Pupils learn in different manner. The way how they learn can be influenced by several factors. These pupils spend longer time in school studying and are perceived to learn and influenced more by their teachers, classmates, the school heads and even the school curriculum. There are even instances when these young minds believe what their teachers and principals say rather than their parents. Moreover, experts also say that the curriculum itself strongly affects the learners. This is one of the reasons why the K to 12 curriculum was finally implemented by the Department of Education. According to the department, the K to 12 curriculum will make the Filipino graduates to be work ready, business ready and university ready. It is in this study that the researcher would want to determine if factors such as the teachers, principals, and the curriculum may influence the learning outcomes of the intermediate pupils.

Learning outcomes describe the extent of significant learnings that pupils or students have achieved. These will tell us what learners have known and what they can do with their learnings. Learning outcomes will determine if teachers have been effective and efficient in teaching their lessons. This may also serve to determine if principals are also doing well in their jobs.

Students' achievement or learning outcomes plays an important role in producing the best quality graduates who will become great leaders and manpower for the community and the country. These students greatly contribute for the country's economic and social development. It is then necessary that they have desirable learning outcomes to be an

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asset of the community and help to make it a progressive one. This study will be conducted to determine if learning outcomes of the pupils are affected by factors such as the principals' instructional leadership, teachers' participation and the K to 12 curriculum.

Learning outcomes can be affected by various factors. In the generation of today's learners, their attention span is so short such that they easily get distracted. This is the reason why teachers have hard time when dealing with the issues and concerns related to improving learners' outcomes. Teachers must be well versed in terms of dealing with these issues because poor learning outcomes may lead to poor performance of the learners in their next level of educational undertakings.

According to (Mushtaq & Khan, 2012), students' learning outcomes measurement has received considerable attention in previous research. There are different factors that may influence learning outcomes. These may range from social, psychological, economic, and environmental to personal factors, but these may vary from person to person and country to country. Measuring of academic performance of students is challenging since student performance is product of socio-economic, psychological, and environmental factors (Hijazi & Naqvi, 2006).

Academic achievement of students especially at the elementary school level is not only a pointer to the effectiveness or otherwise of schools but a major determinant of the future of youths and the nation in general. Learning outcomes have become a phenomenon of interest to all and this account for the reason why scholars have been working hard to untangle factors that militate against good academic performance (Dev, 2016).

School leadership is a major determining factor of the quality of education and school performance. Leadership is essential in improving school management and raising standards of education. The quality of education depends on the nature of leadership provided by the school principal, his or her ability to control, direct and guide teachers and students. The quality of leadership also plays a vital role in students' achievement as it is concerned with teachers, pupils, rules, regulations, and policies that govern the school (Kiptum, 2018).

One dimension of school leadership is instructional leadership. Instructional leadership which was developed in 1980s views the principal as the primary source of educational expertise. Aimed at standardizing the practice of effective teaching, the principal's role was to maintain high expectations for teachers and students, supervise classroom instruction, coordinate the school's curriculum, and monitor student progress. For principals who lacked the skills to accomplish these tasks, coaching and on-site assistance were in short supply (Marks & Printy, 2013).

There are five leadership behaviors that are as important instructional leadership behaviors performed by principals either almost always or frequently by one hundred percent of the principals. These five instructional leadership behaviors are: use data on student academic performance when developing the school's academic goals, set high standards for the percentage of students who are expected to master important instructional objectives, encourage teachers to start class on time and teach to the end of the period, make known what is expected of students at different grade levels, support teachers when they enforce academic policies (Woods & Martin, 2016).

In addition, (Carandang, 2017), stated that to make significant school reform, principals need to understand the interconnectedness of sound human resource management policies, quality curriculum framework, best practices, high expectations of teaching, authentic assessment of learning and a commitment to quality school improvement based on data.

According to (Matz, 2017), instructional leadership and teacher leadership both contribute to improved student performance and school improvement. Specific elements of instructional leadership are found to have a positive correlation with improved student performance. These elements include ensuring teachers are accountable to high instructional standards, fostering a shared vision among faculty and administration for the school, putting an effective school administrator in place, and sustaining a school improvement team.

Curriculum also plays an essential part on the learning outcomes of the pupils as well as on how teachers deliver the content of the curriculum. When the Department of Education fully implemented the K to 12 curriculum in 2012, changes in the Philippine educational system had been a great challenge especially on the part of the teachers who are the front liners in the education system.

Teachers who are teaching under the new curriculum were trained regionally and comprehensively. During summer vacation, K to 12 teacher is gathered to be taught about the new curriculum, the subject matter- its content and scope,

and about assessing the learning outcomes of the pupils/ students. Sadly, there are teachers today who are teaching under K to 12 Curriculum yet never received any training from the Department of Education (Madera, 2015).

Teachers who have been trained are more exposed to different teaching pedagogies in the K to 12 curriculum. This may enable them to be more effective and efficient in delivering their lessons. According to (Garcia, 2017), the teacher qualities and capabilities also affect the performance of the students in their studies. Some of these attributes include teaching experience, teachers' attitude towards the learners, and teacher training.

Meanwhile, (Perez, 2016) mentioned in her study that teacher needs information about the child's home and its influences. The more a teacher knows about home conditions and social factors affecting the child's progress at school, the better he/she can guide a child in his/her activities.

In the light of the preceding situations, this study which will be gauged to determine the impact of the principals, instructional leadership, teachers' participation, and the K to 12 curriculum will be conducted.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

This study focused on the instructional leadership, teachers' participation, and the K to 12 curriculum and its impact on the learning outcomes of the Grade VI pupils in the twelve central elementary schools from the four EDDIS in the Division of Bulacan during the school year 2018-2019.

Specifically, sought to find answers for the following problems:

1. How may the instructional leadership of the principals as perceived by the teachers and principals be described as to:
 - Assessment for learning;
 - Adapting existing programs;
 - Implementing programs for instructional improvement; and
 - Instructional supervision?
2. How may the teachers' participation as perceived by the principals, teachers and pupils be described in terms of;
 - Social regard for learning;
 - Learning environment;
 - Curriculum; and
 - Planning, assessing and reporting; and
 - Classroom Evaluation?
3. How may the perceptions of the principals and teachers in the K to 12 curriculum be described as to:
 - Curriculum;
 - Personal;
 - Learners' welfare; and
 - Perceived problems?
4. How may the pupils' learning outcomes be described as to their general weighted average?
5. Is there a significant difference on the perceptions of the principals and teachers as to:
 - Instructional leadership;
 - Teachers' participation; and
 - K to 12 curriculum?
6. Is there a significant difference on the perceptions of the teachers and pupils on teachers' participation?
7. Is there a significant relationship of instructional leadership, teachers' participation, and K to 12 curriculum on pupils' learning outcomes?

What are the perceptions of the respondents on the importance of instructional leadership, teachers' participation and K to 12 curriculum on enhancing pupils' learning outcomes?

1.2. Hypotheses

This study was guided by the following hypotheses:

- There is no significant difference on the perceptions of the principals and teachers as to instructional leadership, teachers' participation and K to 12 curriculum.
- There is no significant difference on the perceptions of the teachers and pupils on teachers' participation.
- There is no significant relationship of instructional leadership, teachers' participation, and K to 12 curriculum on pupils' learning outcomes.

1.3. Conceptual Framework

This study was premised on the Theories of Educational Leadership. According to (Santamaria, 2016), educational leadership is the professional practice of a leader (or leaders) in an administrative role(s) working with, guiding, and influencing educators in a particular context toward improving learning and other educational processes in early childhood education centers and in elementary, secondary, and postsecondary institutions. These people are most often individuals or small teams employed as school site leaders, principals, and assistant or associate administrators. In early childhood, higher education, or other educational settings these individuals may serve as center director, head of school, department chair, academic dean, provost, or president. Theories of educational leadership have origins in the United States, where frameworks have been drawn largely from industry and commerce management principles. Leadership theories and practices drawn from business-oriented frames of reference have been adopted and adapted for use in educational settings in the United States and similarly developed nations. Therefore, theories of educational leadership have been derived from a diversity of interdisciplinary conceptualizations and models over time. As a result, theories of leadership can be considered emergent, dynamic, and subject to further evolution. In fact, every theory of educational leadership is subject to investigation by researchers in educational centers, schools, and university settings who seek to better understand the dynamics of leadership in a variety of educational contexts. Beyond seminal notions and ideations of educational leadership, developing and sometimes groundbreaking theories contribute to the existing canonical literature in the field. Nonetheless, most theories of educational leadership comprise key elements, which often include capabilities, approaches, and practices. A closer look at these elements further reveals theoretical types of educational leadership (e.g., styles, traits, behaviors), characteristics of educational leadership (e.g., management versus leadership, power, coercion, conceptual frameworks), or the activities or practices educational leaders engage in as expressions of their leadership in action (e.g., approaches, ways of leading). Each element is dependent on the educational context within which it occurs and warrants the consideration of multiple and international perspectives for relevance in diverse and global societies in the 21st century. Therefore, this article includes a representative sampling of influential textbooks, handbooks, journals, and relevant literature as exemplars of sources to explain, illuminate, introduce, interrogate, and evaluate a variety of educational leadership theories.

There is great interest in educational leadership in the early part of the 21st century. This is because of the widespread belief that the quality of leadership makes a significant difference to school and student outcomes. In many parts of the world, including South Africa, there is recognition that schools require effective leaders and managers if they are to provide the best possible education for their learners. As the global economy gathers pace, more governments are realizing that their main assets are their people and that remaining, or becoming, competitive depends increasingly on the development of a highly skilled workforce. This requires trained and committed teachers but they, in turn, need the leadership of highly effective principals and the support of other senior and middle managers (Bush, 2007).

Principal's educational leadership has a greater total association with student learning because of its indirect effect through teacher peer influence. This implies that principals are an important factor in student learning, in part because of their indirect influence on teacher instruction through the collaboration and communication around instruction between peer teachers (Sirinides, 2009).

According to (Kolu, 2015) principals have the most potential to initiate and sustain improvement in academic and other areas of student performance and achievement. Principals are thought to have the most critical role in improving the quality of the school by reforming strategies toward improved students' results and a learning climate conducive for maximum achievement.

This study was also premised on the Theory of Performance (Elger, 2010). This theory postulates that humans can do extraordinary accomplishments. The Theory of Performance (ToP) develops and relates six foundational concepts (italicized) to form a framework that can be used to explain performance as well as performance improvements. To perform is to produce valued results. A performer can be an individual or a group of people engaging in a collaborative effort. Developing performance is a journey, and level of performance describes location in the journey. Current level of performance depends holistically on six components: context, level of knowledge, levels of skills, level of identity,

personal factors, and fixed factors. Three axioms are proposed for effective performance improvements. These involve a performer’s mindset, immersion in an enriching environment, and engagement in reflective practice.

According to (Essays, 2017) the implication of performance theory is that many individuals, going about their ‘everyday businesses are not being themselves all the time. They are acting out roles, predetermined to the point of being programmed in some cases. Performing in everyday life involves people in a wide range of activities from solo or intimate performances behind closed doors to small group activities to interacting as part of a crowd.

This study also encompasses the Social Constructivism Theory of Jean Piaget. Social constructivism is a theory of knowledge in sociology and communication theory that examines the knowledge and understandings of the world that are developed jointly by individuals. This theory assumes that understanding, significance, and meaning are developed in coordination with other human beings. The most important elements in this theory are (a) the assumption that human beings rationalize their experience by creating a model of the social world and the way that it functions and, (b) the belief in language as the most essential system through which humans construct reality (Amineh & Asl, 2015).

According to (Draper, 2013) social constructivism emphasizes that all cognitive functions including learning are dependent on interactions with others (e.g., teachers, peers, and parents). Therefore, learning is critically dependent on the qualities of a collaborative process within an educational community, which is situation specific, and context bound. However, learning must also be seen as more than the assimilation of new knowledge by the individual, but also as the process by which learners are integrated into a knowledge community.

Social constructivism maintains that learning is based on real life adaptive problem solving which takes place in a social manner through shared experience and discussion with others such that new ideas are matched against existing knowledge and the learner adapts rules to make sense of the world. Social constructivism places the focus on the learner as part of a social group, and learning as something that emerges from group interaction processes, not as something which takes place within the individual. Learning is seen as an active socially engaged process, not one of a passive development in response to external forces.

Social constructivist theory thus claims that cognition and learning exist in a dialectical relationship with the social world, whereby discussion is utilized to resolve cognitive conflict and as a result produces higher levels of mental functioning.

Figure 1 Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1 shows the paradigm of the study. It indicates that the independent variables are instructional leadership, teachers’ participation and the K to 12 curriculum. The dependent variable is the pupils’ learning outcomes. Instructional Leadership is measured in terms of Assessment for learning, Adapting Existing Programs, Implementing Programs for Instructional Improvement, and Instructional Supervision. Teachers’ participation on the other hand involves the sub-variables which are Social Regard for Learning, Learning Environment, Curriculum, Planning, Assessing and Reporting, and Classroom Evaluation. K to 12 curriculum involves the Curriculum, Personal, Learners’ Welfare and Perceived Problems. The pupils’ learning outcomes on the other will be measured in terms of general weighted average.

1.4. Significance of the Study

Findings of this study may be beneficial to the following:

- Policy Makers. Findings of the study may give them insights on how to develop programs that will enhance the Instructional Leadership among the principals as well as teachers’ participation and pupils’ learning outcomes.

- Principals. Results of the study may help them to have ideas on how to address the issues and concerns regarding the parents' involvement in their respective schools and pupils' learning outcomes as well as in developing their Instructional Leadership.
- Teachers. This study may help the teachers to be more conscious on addressing issues with regards to their pupils' learning outcomes. They may serve as a way for them to exert more effort on developing themselves to give something more to their pupils.
- Pupils. Results of the study may enable the pupils to be more focused on their studies. This may enable them to be more aware of their study habits.
- Other Researchers. This may serve as guide or references for future researchers who would like to conduct a study in the same field of interest.

1.5. Scope and Limitation of the Study

In this study, variables were limited only to the instructional leadership of the principals, teachers' participation, K to 12 curriculum and pupils' learning outcomes as perceived by the principals, teachers, and pupils from twelve central elementary schools in the four EDDIS in the Division of Bulacan. Instructional Leadership was measured in terms of Assessment for learning, Adapting Existing Programs, Implementing Programs for Instructional Improvement, and Instructional Supervision. Teachers' participation on the other hand was measured as to Social Regard for Learning, Learning Environment, Curriculum and Planning, Assessing and Reporting, and Classroom Evaluation. K to 12 curriculum involves the Curriculum, Personal, Learners' Welfare and Perceived Problems. Finally, pupils' learning outcomes was measured in terms of general weighted average.

The respondents of the study included all the principals, Grade 6 teachers and randomly selected Grade 6 pupils. It was conducted in second semester of the School Year 2018 - 2019.

1.6. Location of the Study

Source: <https://www.bulacan.gov.ph/generalinfo/politicalsubdivision.php>

Figure 2 Location Map of the Study

This study was conducted in twelve central elementary schools from the four EDDIS in the Division of Bulacan. Schools in EDDIS I will include Hagonoy East Central School, Hagonoy West Central School, and Paombong Central School. EDDIS II were Baliuag North Central School, Baliuag South Central School, and Plaridel Elementary School. San Ildefonso Elementary School, Pinaod Central School, and San Miguel Elementary School were the schools from EDDIS III. And from

EDDIS IV, schools that were included are Parada Elementary School, C.M. de Jesus Elementary School, and Sta. Maria Elementary School.

1.7. Definition of Terms

To ensure in-depth understanding of the words used in this study, the following terms were defined operationally:

Adapting existing programs – Refers to one of the dimensions on instructional leadership which is the ability of principals to use research, expertise and other vehicles to assist in developing and implementing a coherent and responsive school-wide curriculum.

Assessment for learning – it refers the element of instructional leadership which focus on how the principal ensure utilization of a range of assessment processes to assess student performance.

Class participation – it is the manner on how the pupils engage themselves during class discussions and how they behave as far as their study is concerned.

Comprehension – it is the ability of the pupils to adjust across all the subjects they are being taught by their teachers.

Curriculum – it refers to how the teachers carry out their lessons effectively and efficiently.

Developing Programs and/or Adapting Existing Programs – is refers to when the principals address deficiencies and sustain successes of current programs in collaboration with teachers and learners.

Implementing Programs for Instructional Improvement – it is the ability of the principals to organize teams to champion instructional innovation programs toward curricular responsiveness.

Instructional Supervision – it refers to the duty of the principals to provide in a collegial manner timely, accurate and specific feedback to teachers regarding their performance.

Learners' welfare – it refers to the impact of the K to 12 curriculum as perceived by the respondents themselves.

Learning Environment – it pertains to the ability of the teachers to create an environment that promote fairness and making the classroom conducive to learning.

Perceived problems – pertains to the problems which are encountered by the respondents as regards to the K to 12 programs.

Personal – it pertains to the perception of the respondents on K to 12 which focus on their personal belief on the implementation of the program.

Planning, Assessing and Reporting – the ability of the teachers to develop and utilize appropriate instructional plan.

Social regard for learning – refers to the characteristic of teachers that deal with punctuality, appropriate appearance, and utilizing various learning experiences and resources.

Task performance – it refers to how the pupils participate in group discussions and how they effort to cope with the daily activities.

Total Population – it refers to the kind of sampling where all the population of a group of people are taken as respondents in the study.

2. Material and methods

This chapter discusses the methods and techniques that were employed in the study. It describes the research design, data gathering techniques, sampling procedure, the respondents of the study, and the statistical tools which will be used in the analysis and interpretation of data.

2.1. Research Design

This study utilized the mixed methods design specifically the sequential explanatory design.

Mixed methods research is the type of research in which a researcher or team of researchers combines elements of qualitative and quantitative research approaches (e. g., use of qualitative and quantitative viewpoints, data collection, analysis, inference techniques) for the broad purposes of breadth and depth of understanding and corroboration Johnson, Onwuegbuzie, & Turner (2007).

According to Wisdom & Creswell (2013), the term mixed methods refer to an emergent methodology of research that advances the systematic integration or mixing of quantitative and qualitative data within a single investigation or sustained program of inquiry.

In the quantitative phase of this study, the researcher conducted a survey among the principals, Grade 6 teachers and pupils to determine the instructional leadership, teachers' participation, K to 12 curriculum and its relationship on pupils' learning outcomes.

As to the qualitative phase of the study, the respondents' perceptions on how instructional leadership, teachers' participation, K to 12 curriculum affect the pupils' learning outcomes will be obtained through a semi-structured interview which was conducted personally by the researcher to the selected respondents.

The results of both the quantitative and qualitative aspect of the study was then analyzed and connected with each other to help to make the results of the study more meaningful and in depth.

2.2. Data Gathering Techniques

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Bulacan to conduct the study in the elementary schools in the Division of Bulacan. Once the permit is approved, the researcher coordinated with the principals of school respondents for the schedule of the administration of survey questionnaires and interview. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires and conduct the interview for the accuracy and reliability of the data.

The main research instrument that was utilized in gathering the necessary data for this study are survey questionnaires. The questionnaire which is composed of three (3) parts are adapted and modified by the researcher based on how it would suit the respondents of the study. Part I of the questionnaire which was adapted from the National Competency-Based Standards for School Heads (2012) measures the Instructional Leadership of the principals. The second part which is about the teachers' participation is adapted from the (National Competency Based Teacher Standards, 2010) and the third part which consists of the K to 12 curriculum was adapted and modified from (Ramos, 2018).

For the qualitative part of the study, open-ended questions were made by the researcher. These questions were asked by the researcher to the randomly selected respondents chosen through fishbowl method in the interview process. The interview is semi-structured. The respondents were asked individually by the researcher. During the process, the researcher used voice recorder and sought assistance of a friend who served as secretary to take down notes.

2.3. Sampling Procedures

The study has three sets of respondents which included the principals, grade 6 teachers and pupils in the twelve central elementary schools from four EDDIS in the Division of Bulacan.

Total population was used for the principal and teacher respondents. On the other hand, sample size using the method of (Cristobal & Cristobal, 2017) was utilized to determine the pupil respondents. According to them, the minimum acceptable sample size for descriptive research is ten percent to twenty percent. After getting the ten percent of the Grade 6 pupils who served as respondents, they were further chosen individually through fishbowl technique.

The researcher interviewed two (2) teachers, and two (2) pupils in every school as part of the data gathering for the qualitative phase of the study. According to (Latham, 2018) qualitative studies involve saturation. It is an instance when a researcher no longer learns very much from the interviews being conducted. At this point, the researcher may stop the process and start analyzing the answers of respondents. Saturation often occurs around twelve (12) participants in homogenous groups. Moreover, he stated that fifteen (15) as a minimum for most qualitative studies works very well when participants are homogenous.

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents of the Study

DISTRICT	SCHOOL	Principals	Grade 6 Teachers	Grade 6 Pupils	
				N	n
EDDIS I					
Hagonoy East	Hagonoy East Central School	1	9	234	23
Hagonoy West	Hagonoy West Central School	1	5	175	18
Paombong	Paombong Central School	1	9	285	29
EDDIS II					
Baliuag North	Baliuag North Central School	1	7	245	25
Baliuag South	Baliuag South Central School	1	6	158	16
Plaridel	Plaridel Elementary School	1	11	309	31
EDDIS III					
San Ildefonso North	San Ildefonso Elementary School	1	6	196	20
San Ildefonso South	Pinaod Central School	1	6	189	19
San Miguel South	San Miguel Elementary School	1	12	324	32
EDDIS IV					
Sta. Maria East	Parada Elementary School	1	5	187	19
Sta. Maria West	C.M. de Jesus Elementary School	1	14	464	46
Sta. Maria Central	Sta. Maria Elementary School	1	10	321	32
TOTAL		12	100	3087	310
GRAND TOTAL		422			

According to (Crouch & McKenzie, 2006), for practicality purposes, less than twenty (20) participants in qualitative study will enable researchers to make a close relationship and thus will improve the open and frank exchange of information. They also mentioned that the sample size for qualitative research is fifteen (15) to twenty (20) interview participants. Thus, the researcher only interviewed two (2) teachers, and two (2) pupils in every school.

2.4. Data Analysis Scheme

Once all the necessary data are completed, these were subjected to statistical analysis. Some statistical tools were utilized to analyze the data for the different variables involved in the study.

Weighted mean was computed to describe the instructional leadership, teachers' participation, K to 12 curriculum and pupils' learning outcomes as perceived by principals, teachers, and pupils.

T-test analysis was utilized to determine if significant difference exists on the perceptions of the principals, teachers and pupils on instructional leadership, teachers' participation, K to 12 curriculum and pupils' learning outcomes.

Pearson Correlation was utilized to determine if significant relationship existed on instructional leadership, teachers' participation, K to 12 curriculum and pupils' learning outcomes.

3. Results and discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data collected and the results of the statistical treatment employed in the study.

3.1. Instructional Leadership

Instructional leadership is learning-focused, learning for both students and adults, and learning which is measured by improvement in instruction and in the quality of student learning. The results of the descriptive measure for this variable are presented from Table 2 to Table 5.

3.2. Assessment for learning

Assessment for learning basically deals with the element of instructional leadership which focus on how the principal ensure utilization of a range of assessment processes to assess student performance. Principals need to ensure that various assessment approaches are utilized by teachers to gauge what the students have learned and have difficulties at. Table 2 indicates the descriptive measure of instructional leadership in terms of assessment for learning.

It can be noted from the table that all the items obtained mean responses that belong to the highest verbal description of always. Four were given by the principals with the highest mean rating of 5.00 with the verbal description of always. These items were about the principal manage the processes and procedures in monitoring student achievement, ensure utilization of a range of assessment processes to assess student performance, assess the effectiveness of curricular/co-curricular programs and/or instructional strategies and utilize assessment results to improve learning. Responses of the teachers on the other hand have recorded mean scores that fall on the verbal description of “always” on all the five statements. The statement regarding the utilization of assessment results to improve learning got the lowest mean response of 4.46 from the teachers.

Table 2 Descriptive Measure of Instructional Leadership in terms of Assessment for Learning

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Manage the processes and procedures in monitoring student achievement	5.00	A	4.52	A
Ensure utilization of a range of assessment processes to assess student performance	5.00	A	4.48	A
Assess the effectiveness of curricular/co-curricular programs and/or instructional strategies	5.00	A	4.51	A
Utilize assessment results to improve learning	5.00	A	4.46	A
Create & manage a school process to ensure student progress is conveyed to students and parents/guardians regularly	4.92	A	4.50	A
Overall Mean	4.98	A	4.49	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

Results implied that the principals, being instructional leaders, see to it that the progress of learners are being evaluated by the teachers through various forms of assessment. These are in the form of formative and summative assessments to gauge their strong and weak points and to further determine if they need enrichment or reinforcement activities.

In the same manner to Bhengu & Mkhize (2013), management practices have positive influence on learner achievement. When school principals focus on effective teaching and instructional leadership practices, improved learner achievement is achieved.

Likewise, Genove (2016) opined that instructional leaders are expected to speak for teachers, establish the direction of instruction, know, and interpret research findings, demonstrate, and explain best practices, take risks in instruction, work well with and support teachers, encourage sharing, spread a sense of where the school is headed instructionally, and help teachers assess and evaluate their impact.

Moreover, Oracion (2014) mentioned that as instructional leaders, principals should create an environment within the school that is conducive to teaching and learning, implement the school curriculum and being accountable for higher

learning outcomes, introduce new and innovative modes of instruction to achieve higher learning outcomes, and encourage staff development.

3.3. Adapting existing programs

Adapting school programs involves the manner of how the principals implement programs for the schools to prosper. Benchmarking is one way to be able to find programs that may be utilized in schools for school improvement. Through benchmarking activities, principals can have ideas of the best practices from other schools which they may employ in their own schools. The descriptive measure on adapting existing programs is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Descriptive Measure of Instructional Leadership in terms of Adapting Existing Programs

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Adapt a research-based school program	4.25	A	4.37	A
Assist in implementing an existing, coherent, and responsive school-wide curriculum	4.75	A	4.45	A
Address deficiencies and sustain successes of current programs in collaboration with teachers and learners	4.75	A	4.42	A
Develop a culture of functional literacy	4.58	A	4.43	A
Cultivate existing programs for learners' improvements and progresses	4.83	A	4.44	A
Overall Mean	4.63	A	4.42	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

It can be observed in the table that all items have obtained a mean rating that fall under the bracket of the highest verbal description which is always. The overall mean response of the principals which is 4.63 is higher compared with that of the teachers which is 4.42. The statement "Cultivate existing programs for learners' improvements and progresses" obtained the highest mean response from the group of principals with the value of 4.83 while the lowest mean response with the value of 4.25 was recorded on the statement "adapting a research-based school program" was recorded from the group of teachers.

Results implied that the principals ensure that the programs being implemented in their schools are for the well-being of the pupils, teachers, and the school. They initiate programs that are not merely intuitions but rather research based. They convene with the teachers and learners to be able to solve issues and concerns in the school.

Similarly, Arias (2014), concurred that school principals are the key leaders in the educational system. They are responsible of the realization of the school vision and mission. They play essential roles in making schools function efficiently. They are involved in all aspects of the school's operation. They are the leaders responsible in providing leadership in the development and implementation of all educational programs and projects in the school. They play a vital role in achieving the government's aim to provide quality basic education.

In the same vein, Cruz et. al. (2016), mentioned that principals' work and responsibilities are complex and thus require a full range of leadership and management knowledge, skills, competencies, and standards. Principals who are skilled in leadership and management techniques are imperative for schools to promotes lifelong learning, raise student achievement, uphold high teaching standard, and advocate school improvement.

3.4. Implementing programs for instructional improvement

School principals have vital role in implementing programs that promote instruction. They serve as the captain of the school who gives the direction where it will go. This study examined how principals implement programs for instructional improvement as it is necessary on pupils' learning outcomes. The results of the descriptive data for this study variable are manifested in Table 4.

Table 4 Descriptive Measure of Instructional Leadership in terms of Implementing Programs for Instructional Improvement

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Manage the introduction of curriculum initiatives in line with DepEd policies (e.g. BEC, Madrasah)	4.83	A	4.46	A
Work with teachers in curriculum review	4.58	A	4.42	A
Enrich curricular offerings based on local needs	4.67	A	4.46	A
Manage curriculum innovation and enrichment with the use of technology	4.75	A	4.53	A
Organize teams to champion instructional innovation programs toward curricular responsiveness	4.75	A	4.46	A
Overall Mean	4.72	A	4.47	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

It can be noticed in the table that all the mean ratings given by the principals and teachers fall under the verbal description of always including the overall mean responses which values are 4.72 and 4.47 respectively. The statement “Manage the introduction of curriculum initiatives in line with DepEd policies (e.g., BEC, Madrasah)” obtained the highest mean score of 4.83 from the principals while the least was on the statement “Work with teachers in curriculum review” with the mean score of 4.58. Meanwhile, the teachers have given the highest rating of 4.53 on the statement “Manage curriculum innovation and enrichment with the use of technology” and their least rated items was “Work with teachers in curriculum review” with 4.42.

Results implied that the principals collaborate with the teachers in the implementation and review of the curriculum. They apply the principle of localization to address the needs of the learners. They innovate based on the available local resources to suit the curriculum to the learners.

According to Inclusive Schools Network (2018), principals play a key role in the delivery of quality instruction. Their responsibilities include ensuring educational strategies are in place that support effective learning for all students. They serve as a facilitator, guide, and supporter of quality instructional practices. Good principals understand that improved test scores are important but know that quality instruction is essential for improving student achievement.

Principals’ leadership influence learning outcomes through their influence on other people or features of the school such as decisions about class size, student-grouping and instructional practices of teachers, the nature and extent of monitoring student progress, provision of professional development opportunities for teachers, and the alignment among goals, programs, and policies (Luna, 2012). Thus, principals should focus on instructional improvement to prepare the learners for life-long learning and survival.

3.5. Instructional supervision

Instructional supervision encompasses the manner on how the principals give technical assistance to teachers to help them improve instruction. Principals need to supervise teachers regardless of their position to assess their instructional competence. This will also serve as a channel for them to come up with instructional plan for struggling and proficient teachers. This will also give them idea on which aspect do their teachers are needing of technical assistance. The descriptive measure of Instructional Leadership in terms of Instructional Supervision is presented in Table 5.

Table 5 Descriptive Measure of Instructional Leadership in terms of Instructional Supervision

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Prepare and implement an instructional supervisory plan	5.00	A	4.44	A
Conduct Instructional Supervision using appropriate strategy	4.92	A	4.48	A
Evaluate lesson plans as well as classroom and learning management	5.00	A	4.56	A
Provide in a collegial manner timely, accurate and specific feedback to teachers regarding their performance	4.92	A	4.47	A
Provide expert technical assistance and instructional support to teachers	4.83	A	4.39	A
Overall Mean	4.93	A	4.47	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

Based on the table, the overall mean scores were 4.93 for the principals and 4.47 for the teachers. The highest mean score of 5.00 was recorded from the principal respondents on two items which are “Prepare and implement an instructional supervisory plan” and “Evaluate lesson plans as well as classroom and learning management”. The least rated item by the principals was “Provide expert technical assistance and instructional support to teachers” which value is 4.83. As to the group of the teachers, the highest mean of 4.56 was the statement “Evaluate lesson plans as well as classroom and learning management” and they rated the item “Provide expert technical assistance and instructional support to teachers” with the least (4.39).

This implied that the principals monitor the teachers regularly to ensure that they don’t go away with the learning competencies prescribed by the Department of Education when teaching. They do this through classroom observations and Learning Action Cells (LAC). During LAC sessions, teachers were given the opportunity to be mentored by the principals for them to improve on their craft.

Results were found to be in accordance with Sindhvad (2009) wherein he wrote in his study that principals have responsibility in four areas. One of which is instructional supervision. It is the responsibility of the principal which is most directly associated with the quality of teaching. It is important to understand in terms of expecting school principals to spearhead any school improvement efforts towards student achievement by focusing mainly on how the teachers deliver instruction.

In the interview, the teachers stressed the importance of proper technical assistance for them to improve classroom instruction and promote higher learning outcomes. Several teachers said that classroom observations must be done properly with pre and post conferences so that they will know the points where they are strong at and where they need rooms for improvement. Result of the interview implies that teachers recognize the relevance of classroom observations as an essential way to trace the weakness of the teachers and help them turn these weaknesses to strengths by means of proper mentoring and coaching and giving expert technical assistance.

3.6. Teachers’ Participation

Teachers’ participation on this study consists of social regard for learning, learning environment, curriculum, planning, assessing, and evaluating and classroom evaluation. Results for these study variables were presented from Table 6 to Table 10.

3.7. Social regard for learning

Social regard for learning refers to the characteristic of teachers that deal with punctuality, appropriate appearance, and utilizing various learning experiences and resources. It is necessary to determine how punctual the teachers are because it can also be a factor that influence their work engagement in school. The analysis on the descriptive measure of teachers’ participation in terms of Social Regard for Learning is shown in Table 6.

Table 6 Descriptive Measure of Teachers' Participation in terms of Social Regard for Learning

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)		Pupils (n=310)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Implements school policies and procedures.	4.92	A	4.73	A	4.62	A
Demonstrates punctuality.	4.75	A	4.67	A	4.74	A
Maintains appropriate appearance.	4.92	A	4.73	A	4.77	A
Careful about the effect of one's behaviour on students.	4.92	A	4.71	A	4.83	A
Makes use of various learning experiences and resources.	4.83	A	4.63	A	4.81	A
Overall Mean	4.87	A	4.69	A	4.75	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

It is noticeable in the table that the principals, teachers, and pupils have given high mean scores on the given items. All the statements obtained the mean ratings that falls on the range of the verbal description always. Among the three groups of respondents, it can be noticed that the principals have given the highest overall mean rating of 4.87 followed by the pupils with 4.75 and the teachers with 4.69. The highest mean score of 4.92 was recorded on three statements which are about the teachers implement school policies and procedures, maintains appropriate appearance, and careful about the effect of one's behavior on students.

Results implied that the teachers are mindful of their role on promoting the learning outcomes of their pupils. They ensure that the pupils were able to acquire the competencies they are supposed to exhibit by providing them with learning activities that enable them to develop their skills. They are also effective and efficient such that they finish the tasks assigned to them on time.

Results were found in conformance to Barberos, Gozalo, & Padayogdog (2019) as they mentioned in their study that the teachers, being the focal figure in education, must be competent and knowledgeable to impart the knowledge they could give to the learners.

Accordingly, Magsayo (2009) found out in her study that teacher quality affects performance of learners. One of the qualities of the teachers that was found to have significant correlation was teachers' highest educational attainment. It showed that teachers who have reached higher level of education are more likely to produce better performing learners.

The teachers pointed out the importance of teachers' participation on pupils' learning outcomes during the interview. A number of teachers mentioned that teachers are the front liners in the education system thus they must be competent and equipped with teaching skills that will ensure quality learning among the pupils. One teacher also said that the greatest responsibility of teachers is to teach, and they must have their own initiative how to enhance their own teaching skills. They also emphasized that teachers play a very important role in promoting pupils' learning outcomes thus they should always establish harmonious relationship with their pupils for them to gain their respect and this would make them easier for the pupils to be more cooperative and obedient. The pupils interviewed also said that teachers are the key individuals that help them in progressing not only in school but in life as well. They said that their teachers serve as their second parents who keep on inspiring and encouraging them to always do their best. A number of pupils also noted that whenever they commit mistakes, their teachers are there to cheer them up and give them inspiration to keep going and learn from their mistakes.

3.8. Learning environment

Learning environment basically pertains to the classroom where the teaching and learning process usually takes place. A learning environment that is conducive to learning will more likely motivate the pupils and will enable them to be more participative in and focused on class. This study also explored on how the teachers make the learning environment conducive to learning. Table 7 reveals the results for the descriptive measure of teachers' participation in terms of Learning Environment.

Table 7 Descriptive Measure of Teachers Participation in terms of Learning Environment

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)		Pupils (n=310)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Creates an environment that promotes fairness	4.83	A	4.74	A	4.71	A
Makes the classroom environment safe and conducive to learning	4.75	A	4.75	A	4.84	A
Communicates higher learning expectations to each learner	4.75	A	4.59	A	4.73	A
Establishes and maintains consistent standards of learners' behavior.	4.92	A	4.58	A	4.74	A
Creates a healthy psychological climate for learning	4.83	A	4.68	A	4.65	A
Overall Mean	4.82	A	4.67	A	4.73	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

It can be gleaned from the table that the overall mean ratings were highest among the principals (4.82), followed by the pupils (4.73) and the teachers (4.67). The highest mean response obtained from the principal respondents was 4.92 on the item “establish and maintain consistent standards of learners' behaviour”. The teachers and pupils gave their highest mean response of 4.75 and 4.84 respectively on the item “Makes the classroom environment safe and conducive to learning”. The least rated item by the principals (4.75) was recorded on two statements which are “Makes the classroom environment safe and conducive to learning”, and “Communicates higher learning expectations to each learner”. The least rating given by the teachers was on the item “Establishes and maintains consistent standards of learners' behaviour” with 4.58 mean rating while the lowest among the pupils was on the statement “Creates a healthy Psychological climate for learning”.

Results implied that the teachers recognize the importance of creating a learning environment that is conducive to learning. They find ways and means to make their classrooms a place where their pupils will be able to learn and have fun at the same time. They also exhibit their being objective by not showing favoritism and treating their pupils equally regardless of who and what they are.

Results of the study conforms to Monilla (2015) wherein it was found out that learning environment affect academic performance of learners. Teaching methods and classroom management are the two elements of learning environment that influence academic performance.

Additionally, Ortiz (2014) stated in her study that classroom environment can help pupils' academic performance rise by 25% over an academic year. Academic performance is significantly correlated with learning environments. Factors like classroom orientation, light or air quality are some of the parameters of an effective learning environment. These must be designed in such a way that the learning environment will be conducive to learning.

The teachers emphasized that they could help in improving the pupils' learning outcomes by creating an environment that is conducive to learning. A number of teachers also said that by making their classrooms well- ventilated, the pupils will be motivated and participative during classroom discussions. The pupils on the other hand also mentioned that their teachers can help them improve their learning outcomes by creating an environment where they can learn and enjoy at the same time. According to them, they must also be engaged in various activities in the classroom that will develop their skills.

3.9. Curriculum

Curriculum refers to how the teachers carry out their lessons effectively and efficiently. It encompasses their learning goals, how they utilize allotted time, the teaching methods they will employ and the use of ICT in teaching and Learning. Table 8 exhibits the descriptive measure of teachers' participation in terms of Curriculum.

Table 8 Descriptive Measure of Teachers' Participation in terms of Curriculum

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)		Pupils (n=310)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Demonstrates mastery of the subject	4.83	A	4.78	A	4.83	A
Communicates clear learning goals for the lessons that are appropriate for learners	4.83	A	4.67	A	4.84	A
Makes good use of allotted instructional time	5.00	A	4.64	A	4.82	A
Selects teaching methods, learning activities and the instructional materials or resources appropriate to the learners, and aligned to objectives of the lesson	4.75	A	4.60	A	4.83	A
Demonstrates skills in the use of ICT in teaching and learning	4.83	A	4.60	A	4.64	A
Overall Mean	4.85	A	4.66	A	4.79	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

As the table shows, all the items in curriculum got the mean score that falls under the verbal description of always. The highest overall mean was recorded from the principals with the value of 4.85 followed by the pupils (4.79) and the teachers (4.66). The highest mean rating was obtained on the statement that the teachers make good use of allotted instructional time while the lowest was on the statements that teachers select teaching methods, learning activities and the instructional materials or resources appropriate to the learners, and aligned to objectives of the lesson and demonstrates skills in the use of ICT in teaching and learning.

This shows that the teachers practice the principle of differentiated instruction. This means that they provide activities and learning opportunities that are suitable on the needs of their pupils. They do not practice the one-size-fits all principle. They take extra effort for differentiated instruction to address individual differences of the learners.

According to Magayon & Tan (2016), Differentiated Instruction (DI) has been found to be effective in catering to the individuality of students and at the same time helping students to have positive attitudes about school, increased engagement in learning, and improved achievement. It motivates students' interest, makes learning mathematics easier, and challenges students to learn and do more.

In the same vein, results in the study of Aranda & Zamora (2016) revealed that the academic performance of the students in the experimental group where differentiated instruction was employed is higher compared to the control group. They concluded that differentiated instruction based on different learning styles was effective in teaching.

During the conducted interview, the respondents were asked about the best practices that enables the pupils achieve the desired learning outcomes. It was common from the responses of both teacher and pupils that differentiated instruction was effective in promoting pupils' learning outcomes. According to them, when pupils are given options to choose from, they tend to bring out the most out of what they do. Differentiated instruction enables the learners to develop and nurture their gift.

This would boil down to the fact that teachers must be well rounded of diverse teaching pedagogies to be used inside the classroom to be able for them to give justice on differentiated instruction. They must keep themselves up to date of the 21st century teaching strategies for them to address their concerns on the individuality of their pupils.

3.10. Planning, assessing and reporting

Planning, assessing, and reporting encompasses the manner of how the teachers design and plan their lessons, how they deliver it and how they gauge the learning that took place among their pupils. Results for planning, assessing, and reporting is shown in Table 9.

Table 9 Descriptive Measure of Teachers Participation in terms of Planning, Assessing and Reporting

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)		Pupils (n=310)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Develops and utilizes creative and appropriate instructional plan.	4.83	A	4.65	A	4.78	A
Develops and uses a variety of appropriate assessment strategies to monitor and evaluate learning.	4.83	A	4.60	A	4.75	A
Monitors regularly and provides feedback on learners' understanding of content.	4.75	A	4.65	A	4.71	A
Conducts regular meetings with learners and parents to report learners' progress	4.75	A	4.64	A	4.65	A
Involves parents to participate in school activities that promote learning.	4.75	A	4.68	A	4.62	A
Overall Mean	4.78	A	4.64	A	4.70	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

As can be observed in the table, the principals have given the highest mean rating of 4.83 on two statements which are the teachers develop and utilize creative and appropriate instructional plan and develop and use a variety of appropriate assessment strategies to monitor and evaluate learning. The lowest mean rating of 4.60 was obtained on the statement about the teachers develop and use a variety of appropriate assessment strategies to monitor and evaluate learning. The lowest and highest mean responses recorded both obtained the highest verbal description of always as well as the overall mean responses of the three groups of respondents.

These results showed that the teachers have carefully designed how they deliver their lessons and how to evaluate their pupils. They also communicate these to the parents through parents and teachers' conferences. Planning the lessons and deciding on how to properly gauge learning outcomes is essential. This way, teachers will determine who learned and who did not, what competencies were mastered and not.

Through using appropriate classroom assessment strategies and techniques, teachers can increase their students' motivation and show them how well they have learned the language. Evaluation goes beyond students' achievements and language assessments to consider all aspects of teaching and learning, and to look at how educational decisions can be informed by the results of alternative forms of assessment and evaluation. It is also giving teachers useful information about how to improve their teaching skills (Jabbarifar, 2009).

If a teacher begins with a well-defined target of intended outcomes, authentic assessments can be rightfully achieved, reflective of what they teach and what learning they could expect from their students. Successful outcomes will then follow when teachers are able to make a clear learning objective towards smooth delivery of the entire lesson (Cuñado, & Abocejo, 2018).

During the interview, the interviewees were asked about the roles of teachers on developing pupils' learning outcomes. They said that teachers are the most important individuals that affect the pupils' learning outcomes. They must always do their best so that they will be able to give what is due to their pupils. They must know and apply different teaching strategies that will suit each pupil that they have. According to them, teachers should not only focus on teaching their pupils, but they should also take effort to know them. They should create a learning environment where pupils will learn and enjoy at the same time. The pupils on the other hand pointed out that teachers need to use different strategies so that they will not be bored. According to them, they learn best when they are taught with various activities such as charades, technology-aided instruction, and simulations. The pupils mentioned that these activities enable them to remember more what their teachers have taught them.

3.11. Classroom Evaluation

Classroom evaluation is usually done by principals and master teachers to assess the teachers and give proper technical assistance for the teachers to improve their teaching skills. This study explored on classroom evaluation to determine how the teachers deliver their lessons. The descriptive measure for classroom evaluation is showed in Table 10.

Table 10 Descriptive Measure of Teachers Participation in terms of Classroom Evaluation

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)		Pupils (n=310)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Applies knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	4.83	A	4.67	A	4.73	A
Uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.	4.92	A	4.56	A	4.33	A
Applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking as well as other higher-order thinking skills.	4.75	A	4.62	A	4.68	A
Manages classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments.	4.83	A	4.64	A	4.34	A
Manages learner behaviour constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments.	4.92	A	4.66	A	4.64	A
Overall Mean	4.85	A	4.63	A	4.54	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

The table exposes that as the rest of the sub-variables in teachers' participation, all item statements under classroom evaluation have also obtained only one verbal description which is always. All the mean ratings given by the principals, teachers and pupils fall under this verbal description. The highest of which is 4.92 was recorded on the statements that the teachers use a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills and manage learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments. The lowest on the other hand with the value of 4.33 was also recorded on the item that the teachers use a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.

These showed that the teachers have high teaching skills. Considering the responses of the principals who are the ones who observe them in their classes, it can be noted that they have commendable teaching performance and that they are equipped with various teaching strategies necessary for them to do differentiated instruction. Result would also imply that the teachers exhibit mastery of the subject matter by incorporating other disciplines as they deliver their lessons.

Just as learners have individual differences, teachers also have their own teaching styles. Regardless of what teaching style a teacher employs, what is important is that they consider what is the most suitable for the type of learners they have.

According to Villena & De Mesa (2015), effective teachers are proactive. They are active information processors particularly in the classroom, good decision makers, and task oriented. They are equipped with knowledge and mastery of content in the fields, aware of the characteristics of their students, and skillful in decision making particularly in keeping their students' tasks.

Teachers may adjust their teaching styles to provide learners with effective learning environment (Tongson, 2018). Teachers should therefore be familiar with the learning styles of their pupils for them to do this. This will enable them to make their activities personalized for their pupils. This way, learners will be more engaged, and they will have the options to do learning activities that will suit them the most.

The teachers pointed out that during the interview that principals need to provide proper technical assistance for them to improve their teaching skills. They must be aware of the capabilities of the teachers so that they will know what technical assistance they must give the teachers. A number of teachers also stressed that principals must empower their teachers by guiding them and supporting them in their craft. The teachers said that when they empowered, they are also motivated. When the pupils were asked about their insights on how principals help the teachers develop their teaching skills, they also mentioned that the principals must guide the teachers especially those who are new in the profession so that they will know how to properly deliver their lessons. Some pupils also said that the principals need to be kind to the teachers so that they will feel comfortable with the principals.

3.12. K to 12 Curriculum

K to 12 curriculum is the new basic education curriculum being implemented by the Department of Education. This study explored on four aspects under this variable. These include curriculum, personal, learners' welfare and perceived problems. Results for the descriptive measures of these study variables are revealed in Tables 11 to 14.

3.13. Curriculum

Curriculum refers to the lessons and academic content taught in a school or in a specific course or program. It encompasses the knowledge and skills students are expected to learn, which includes the learning standards or learning objectives they are expected to meet. Table 11 displays the results from the data gathered in K to 12 Curriculum in terms of Curriculum.

Table 11 Descriptive Measure of K to 12 Curriculum in terms of Curriculum

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
It gives learners time to master competencies and skills as well.	4.67	SA	4.44	SA
Allows learning for a more holistic development.	4.67	SA	4.63	SA
Helps learners to prepare for higher education.	4.75	SA	4.54	SA
It helps make the graduates prepared emotionally for entrepreneurship or employment.	4.67	SA	4.49	SA
Gives learners enough time for other learning opportunities beyond the classroom	4.67	SA	4.49	SA
Overall Mean	4.68	SA	4.52	SA

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

As displayed in the table, the principals and teachers strongly agreed on all the statements given. The principals have given their highest mean rating of 4.75 on the statement the K to 12 curriculum helps learners to prepare for higher education. The lowest mean rating on the other hand was recorded on the responses of the teachers for the statement K to 12 curriculum gives learners time to master competencies and skills as well.

Result showed that the principals and teachers have perceived that the K to 12 curriculum has a positive impact among the pupils. They are optimistic on the decision of the government on the implementation of the new basic education program in the Philippines.

The Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization – Innotech (SEAMEO-Innotech) found that the previous 10-year educational cycle to be congested, with a 12-year curriculum squished into 10 years. As a result, Filipino students have trailed behind students around the world in the areas of math, languages, and science. The new K to 12 curriculum is aimed to fix that (Uyquiengco, 2014).

3.14. Personal

Personal involves the perceptions of the principals and teachers on the K to 12 curriculum. Being the grassroots, it is important to know their perceptions because they are the ones who actually see and experience the problems along with the implementation of the K to 12 curriculum. The descriptive measure for this variable is manifested in Table 12.

Table 12 Descriptive Measure of K to 12 Curriculum in terms of Personal

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
It is remarkable.	4.50	SA	4.38	SA
Just in time and appropriate.	4.42	SA	4.33	SA
It will require additional trainings for teachers.	4.58	SA	4.52	SA
Teachers are well informed about the program and its implementation.	4.58	SA	4.47	SA
Difficult to implement due to lack of materials, equipment, and facilities.	4.58	SA	4.44	SA
Overall Mean	4.53	SA	4.43	SA

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

It can be seen in the table that only one verbal description was recorded among all the statements given. Both the principals and teachers have strongly agreed that the teachers are well informed about the program and its implementation. These items obtained the highest mean score of 4.58 as responded by the principals. However, two other statements also obtained the same mean rating. The principals strongly agreed that the new curriculum will require additional trainings for teachers and is difficult to implement due to lack of materials, equipment, and facilities. These show that however optimistic of the implementation of the K to 12 programs, the principals and teachers recognize the problems along with it.

In the study conducted by Saber (2015), results revealed that the emerging concerns in the implementation of the program includes displacement of teachers in the tertiary level, lack of information concerning the guidelines for implementation, lack of university students for two years and the insufficient resources for the implementation. Despite these concerns, however, administrators find ways to meet these challenges.

Accordingly, Calub (2019) mentioned in her study that for a curriculum to be implemented, knowledge and experience is required to improve competence and positive attitude, this will enable schools to solve problems and implement change. Administrators and teachers need to work together toward a shared vision of excellence in the classroom. If the possibility of achieving excellence is perceived to be remote and unachievable, it will not be taken seriously by school administrators, faculty, and students. But if it can be shown that excellence is realizable, its norms and values can be created and imprinted in the educational culture.

During the interview process, the interviewees were also asked about what principals should do to ensure that pupils will develop the desired learning outcomes. The teachers answered that the principals should see to it that what is being taught by the teachers are those that are within the curriculum as mandated by the Department of Education. Principals must keep themselves aware of what are embedded in the curriculum to make sure that all the programs and activities are aligned with the curriculum. They can do this by conducting regular classroom observation at least once each teacher per grading period. The pupils also pointed out that principals should act as a mentor for their teachers. They said that if they as pupils need their teachers as a guide, their teachers also need the principals to act as their guide.

3.15. Learners' welfare

The benefits that the Filipino learners may gain from the K to 12 curriculum were included in Learners' welfare. The descriptive measures of the K to 12 curriculum in terms of Learners' welfare is presented in Table 13.

Table 13 Descriptive Measure of K to 12 Curriculum in terms of Learners' Welfare

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
It enhances knowledge and skills of the learners.	4.75	SA	4.47	SA
It helps learners to acquire skills which are relevant to have a sustainable life in the future.	4.67	SA	4.39	SA
It will equip the learners with 21 st century skills to compete globally.	4.67	SA	4.39	SA
It helps boost the self-confidence of the learners.	4.50	SA	4.47	SA
It will help produce lifelong learners.	4.67	SA	4.45	SA
Overall Mean	4.65	SA	4.44	SA

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

As can be gleaned from the table, the highest mean rating of 4.75 which has the highest verbal description of strongly agree was given by the principals on the statement that K to 12 curriculum enhances knowledge and skills of the learners. The teachers on the other hand have given their lowest mean rating of 4.39 on two items which states that the K to 12 curriculum helps learners to acquire skills which are relevant to have a sustainable life in the future and will equip the learners with 21st century skills to compete globally.

Results implied that the principals and teachers believe that the K to 12 curriculum is good for the learners. Despite the challenges faced in the implementation of the program, they are optimistic that the program will help the learners prepare for their lives in the futures.

According to Oroña (2014), K to 12 curriculum make students more competent. This will enable the Filipino graduates to compete along with the other graduates in different countries where the curriculum has long been implemented. The curriculum will put Filipino students at par with the rest of the world. This would be a testament that an investment in education is the key toward reaching national growth and development.

3.16. Perceived problems

Along with the implementation of the K to 12 curriculum, there are perceived problems. Perceived problems in this study involves the perceptions of the principals and teachers on the challenges that arise in line with the implementation of the K to 12 curriculum. Results for the descriptive measure of K to 12 Curriculum in terms of Perceived Problems is shown in Table 14.

Table 14 Descriptive Measure of K to 12 Curriculum in terms of Perceived Problems

Item Statement	Principals (n=12)		Teachers (n=100)	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Additional burden to the teachers and students.	2.83	MA	3.23	MA
It will cause additional financial problem.	2.83	MA	3.40	MA
There will be lack of classroom, teachers and non-teaching personnel.	3.08	MA	3.44	A
Substandard quality of education due to lack of resources (e.g. textbooks, laboratory, learning materials).	3.08	MA	3.58	A
It will deprive other siblings to study.	2.58	DA	3.02	MA
Overall Mean	2.88	MA	3.34	MA

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Always (A); 3.41 – 4.20: Frequent (F); 2.61 – 3.40: Sometimes (S); 1.81 – 2.60: Rarely (R); 1.00 – 1.80: Never (N)

As manifested in Table 14, both the principals and teachers obtained overall mean scores which fall under the verbal description moderately agree with values of 2.88 and 3.34 respectively. It can also be noticed in the table that the principals disagreed to the statement “Will deprive other siblings to study” given the lowest mean of 2.58 from the group of teachers. It can also be noticed that the group of teachers agreed on two statements which are “There will be lack of classroom, teachers and non-teaching personnel” and “Substandard quality of education due to lack of resources (e.g., textbooks, laboratory, learning materials)” which mean scores were 3.44 and 3.48 respectively.

The results imply that despite the challenges along with the implementation of the K to 12 curriculum, the teachers and the principals find ways and means to meet these challenges. They are optimistic that this program of the Department of Education will help the Filipino students to be at par with the students in other nations.

Accordingly, Roma (2019), mentioned that change is never easy especially when it is about a big undertaking such as the implementation of the new K to 12 curriculum in the Philippines. It is high time, however, that we join the rest of the world and improve the quality of our basic education system and the graduates.

In addition, Secretary Briones also admitted that the Department of Education faces challenges in the full implementation of the program. According to her, they are facing challenges of finishing school buildings intended for the students and furniture because these are the basic needs. But she expressed her confidence that these problems will be addressed eventually (Manila Times, 2017).

3.17. Pupils' Learning Outcomes

Pupils' learning outcomes in this study is measured in terms of the general weighted average of the pupils. This study focused on this variable to determine if it can be affected by the Instructional Leadership of the Principals, Teachers' Participation and the K to 12 curriculum. It is necessary to know what possible factors may influence pupils' learning outcomes to for teachers and principals to make sound decisions to help pupils develop their learning competencies. Table 15 manifests the frequency distribution and descriptive measures of the pupils' learning outcomes.

Table 15 Frequency and percentage distribution and Descriptive Measures of pupils' learning outcomes

GRADE	f (N = 310)	%	Verbal Description
90 – 100	198	64.0	Outstanding
85 – 89	106	34.0	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	6	2.0	Satisfactory
75 – 79	0	0.0	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75	0	0.0	Did Not Meet Expectations
Range	82 – 98		
Mean	90.55		
Verbal Description	Outstanding		
Standard Deviation	3.032		

It can be gleaned in the table that only two verbal descriptions were recorded from the pupils' learning outcomes. Majority of the pupils obtained average that fall under the verbal description of outstanding with the total of one hundred ninety-eight at sixty four percent. The remaining one hundred six or thirty four percent were very satisfactory. Overall, the mean score of the pupils' learning outcomes can be verbally described as outstanding which numerical value is 90.55.

These results obtained from the pupils' learning outcomes imply that the pupils are performing well in their studies. These desirable learning outcomes of the pupils may be influenced by various factors.

According to the study conducted by Andaya (2016) mentioned that teachers play a significant role on students' academic achievement. Teachers are the best instructional aid that helps learners to achieve the learning competencies that they are supposed to obtain or develop.

During the interview, the respondents were asked about the factors that greatly affects the learning outcomes of the pupils. According to them, one of the most influential factors is the teacher. The manner of how teachers deliver their lessons, how they deal with their pupils have great impact on pupils' performance. They said that teachers must be equipped with necessary skills and competencies for them to motivate their pupils and engage them in classroom activities. They also mentioned about how the principals treat the teachers and pupils. One of the teachers said that proper coaching and mentoring enables teachers to develop their teaching skills thereby also helps them to deliver quality basic education among their pupils. They must be given opportunities for personal and professional growth and development.

Likewise, the interviewees were also asked on which aspect of learning outcomes the pupils excel. They answered that the pupils excel in Science and English. The pupils prefer topics which are related in sciences and they also enjoy whenever they speak the English language during their class. The pupils perceived that these subjects are the most essential in the future when they are already in the field that they will choose to be their careers. This is also the reason why that at this early, they are preparing themselves for the future.

3.18. Significant difference on the perception of principals and teachers as to Instructional Leadership, Teachers' participation, and K to 12 Curriculum

The T-test Analysis on the perceptions of principals and teachers as to Instructional Leadership, Teachers' participation, and K to 12 Curriculum is presented in Table 16.

Table 16 T-test Analysis on the difference of the perception of principals and teachers as to Instructional Leadership, Teachers' participation, and K to 12 Curriculum

ITEM	MEAN		Mean Difference	t-value	p-value
	Principals	Teachers			
Instructional Leadership	4.82	4.46	0.35	3.585**	0.001
Teachers' Participation	4.83	4.66	0.17	1.695ns	0.093
K to 12 curriculum	4.19	4.18	0.01	0.044ns	0.965

Legend : ** highly significant difference ($p \leq 0.01$); ns: no significant difference ($p \geq 0.05$)

It can be noticed in the table that among the three variables, only one was found out to have significant difference and this was Instructional leadership. This significant difference can be derived from the computed probability value of 0.001 which is less than the level of significance. The two other variables which are teachers' participation ($p=0.093$) and K to 12 curriculum ($p=0.0956$) have no statistical significant difference.

Results implied that the perceptions of the principals are higher as compared to the teachers. It can be inferred from this that the principals have greater regard as far as instructional leadership, teachers' participation, and the K to 12 curriculum is concerned. Being the school heads, they are expected to be acquainted of these aspects for them to sail the school to where it should go. They must be competent enough to give due technical assistance to the teachers under his/her supervision. They must motivate them, empower them, and help them bring out the best in them.

Principals should focus on transforming the culture of the school to ensure in an efficient way that teaching and learning functions effectively. They have an indirect effect on teachers' self-efficacy through their influence on collegial support. The principals have crucial role for teachers' well-being, the professional relationships between staff members and their commitment to professional development and school development. They must create number of motivating conditions that encourage teachers to learn and to optimize their practice (Engels et. al., 2008).

In the same manner, Habegger (2008), focused on her study on the different roles of principals which included assuring instruction aligned to state academic content standards, maintaining continuous improvement in the building, designing instruction for student success, developing partnerships with parents and the community, and nurturing a culture where each individual feels valued. She found out that among these roles, creating a positive school culture is the most essential.

The deliberate decision by the principals to focus their time on creating a positive school culture that enables the other areas to prosper. Schools with principals who have created a culture that empowered and instilled confidence in teachers as they prepared for achievement testing, solicited professional dialog and research, valued their students and teachers, and sought the help of parents and community members to enhance school effectiveness are more likely to become high performing.

3.19. Significant difference on the perception of teachers and pupils as to Teachers’ participation

Table 17 unfolds the T-test Analysis on the difference of the perception of teachers and pupils as to Teachers’ participation.

Table 17 T-test Analysis on the difference of the perception of teachers and pupils as to Teachers’ participation

ITEM	MEAN		Mean Difference	t-value	p-value
	Teachers	Pupils			
Teachers’ Participation	4.66	4.71	-0.05	-0.17ns	0.241

Legend : ns no significant difference ($p \geq 0.05$)

As the table exhibits, no significant difference exists on the perceptions of teachers and pupils on teachers’ participation. It can be noted from the computed probability value of 0.241 that is greater than that of the level of significance at 0.05. Looking at the table further, it can also be noticed that the mean difference obtained a negative value. This is because the pupils have given higher mean ratings as compared to the teachers.

This implies that the pupils appreciate how their teachers have taught them. They were able to see how their teachers struggle to be able for them to acquire the quality of education they are supposed to acquire. Teachers are the most influential factor that will help learners to achieve academic success. They must be abreast of the competencies and skills needed for them to deliver the quality of education that the learners deserve.

In the study conducted by Alos, Caranto and David (2015), they have concluded that there are several factors that that pose high impact on the performance of students. These factors included personal condition, study habits, home-related aspect, school-related aspect, and Teacher-related aspect. Among these factors, it was found out that teacher-related factors have the most impact on students’ performance. It was therefore recommended that teachers should be well equipped with teaching strategies, and they should undergo seminars and workshops on this aspect to help them improve classroom instruction.

3.20. Pearson Correlation Analysis of Instructional Leadership, Teachers’ Participation, and K to 12 curriculum on pupils’ learning outcomes

Table 18 Pearson Correlation Analysis of instructional leadership, teachers’ participation, and K to 12 curriculum on pupils’ learning outcomes

ITEM	Pupils’ Learning Outcomes (GWA)
Instructional Leadership	0.254*
	(0.011)
Teachers’ Participation	0.217*
	(0.030)
K to 12 Curriculum	0.193 ^{ns}
	(0.055)

Legend: ns no significant relationship ($p \geq 0.05$); *significant relationship; values enclosed in parenthesis are p-values and the correlation coefficient values (r) are above the p-values

The study also investigated the relationship of Instructional Leadership, Teachers’ Participation and K to 12 Curriculum on Pupils’ Learning Outcomes. Table 18 reveals the Pearson Correlation Analysis of instructional leadership, teachers’ participation, and K to 12 curriculum on pupils’ learning outcomes.

It can be noticed in the table that two variables were found to have significant correlation with pupils' learning outcomes. These were Instructional Leadership and Teachers' Participation. These can be inferred from the computed probability values of 0.011 and 0.030 respectively which are greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Looking at the table further, it can also be noticed that the correlation coefficients are positive with values of 0.254 for Instructional Leadership and 0.217 for teachers' participation. This indicates that when the value of instructional leadership and teachers' participation increases, so as the pupils' learning outcomes will also increase. Meanwhile, K to 12 curriculum was found to have no statistical significance on pupils' learning outcomes ($p=0.055$).

Results imply that both principals and teachers play a vital role on promoting pupils' learning outcomes. They serve to have the most impact on how pupils learn and develop their skills and competencies. Principals and teachers should work together in helping the learners acquire necessary skills they need to succeed in life. Principals should always guide their teachers by giving technical assistance that will help them improve classroom instruction. Teachers on the other hand should always be committed on teaching their pupils the best way they. They should always be resourceful and creative in delivering their lessons to make their lessons engaging enough to motivate their pupils.

Results of the study conforms with Vidon & Grasetti (2003) who mentioned that it is teacher performance that directly affects student performance but quality of leadership matters in determining the motivation of teachers and the quality of their teaching. Instructional leadership of principals that involves the teachers in a process of shaping their schools will cause them to be more motivated and to teach differently. This will make a difference to the learning and motivation of students.

Likewise, Mugambi (2011), cited in his study that there is a significant positive relationship between effective leadership and students' learning and achievement. The principals' skills in school management influence the behaviour of the school in terms of how teachers teach, how much students learn and the overall school performance.

In contrast to the study of Cruickshank (2017), principals have indirect influence on student outcomes. The impact that school leaders can have on student learning is often moderated by other factors including teacher quality, classroom procedures and school environment. More specifically, effective transformational and instructional leadership is closely linked to enhanced organizational culture and effectiveness, as well as increased teacher engagement and commitment.

For schools to become effective, principals should address certain managerial tasks focused on learning outcomes. Principals should be compassionate in terms of instructional leadership. This may be done by doing various instructional activities that impact pupils' learning outcomes such as including provision of teaching and learning resources supervision of teaching/learning processes, visiting classrooms, and checking teachers and students work, employment of teachers, motivating students' progress and promoting teachers' development among others.

Accordingly, Bamidele (2001), stated that the process of supervising a teacher in an instructional setting often involves direct assistance to improve the strategies of classroom practice through observation and evaluation of teacher performance. Effective supervision is seen as one key factor of improving the quality and efficiency of basic education, the quality of educational management and the quality of educational attainment.

In addition, Bilasa (2016), found out in his study that there is a significant relationship between the teachers' competencies and the academic performance of students. Teachers should always be abreast of the skills they need for them to become effective and efficient in the 21st century learning environment. They should never stop learning and must always be hungry of new knowledge. As the front liners in the educational system, they should always embody what the Department of Education mandates to become better partners in the delivery of quality basic education to the learners.

Moreover, Torio and Torio (2015), concluded in their study that teaching pedagogy of teachers have positive effect on academic performance and motivation. Teachers should therefore use strategies that motivate and enhance pupils' learning. These strategies will make learning more fun and interesting and thus will make the pupils more interested of the lessons thereby enabling them to have positive learning outcomes.

This chapter presents the summary of the major findings, the conclusions arrived at based on the findings, and the recommendations given in accordance with the conclusions.

4. Results and discussion

The study focused on Instructional Leadership, Teachers' Participation, K to 12 Curriculum and its impact on pupil's learning outcomes.

In terms of instructional leadership, both the principals and teachers have mean ratings that fall under the verbal description of always. The mean scores of the principals are quite higher as compared to that of the teachers.

In terms of Teachers' Participation, it was found out that the teachers are always doing their roles as far as their teaching profession is concerned. The responses of the principals, teacher and pupils have obtained only one verbal description which is always.

In terms of the K to 12 curriculum, the principals and teachers strongly agreed on almost all statements except of those under the perceived problems which have recorded the lowest mean responses.

The learning outcomes of the pupils as measured in their general weighted average was outstanding.

In terms of the significant differences on the perceptions of the respondents in terms of Instructional Leadership, Teachers' Participation and K to 12 curriculum, highly significant difference was found on Instructional leadership while Teachers' Participation and K to 12 curriculum have no significant differences.

Finally, in terms of the relationship of Instructional Leadership, Teachers' Participation and K to 12 curriculum on pupils' learning outcomes, Instructional Leadership and Teachers' Participations was found to have significant relationship on pupils' learning outcomes. K to 12 curriculum on the other hand was found to have no significant relationship on pupils' leaning outcomes.

5. Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- There is no significant difference on the perceptions of the principals and teachers as to instructional leadership, teachers' participation and K to 12 curriculum.
- There is no significant difference on the perceptions of the teachers and pupils on teachers' participation.
- There is a significant relationship of instructional leadership, teachers' participation on pupils' learning outcomes. There is no significant relationship of K to 12 curriculum on pupils' learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations are proposed:

- The Department of Education should initiate programs and policies that will enhance the Instructional leadership of the principals. This may be in the form of seminars, trainings, and workshops on providing expert technical assistance and instructional support to teachers.
- As instructional leaders, principals must get in classrooms more. They must conduct at least four formal classroom observations each school year each teacher regardless of experience. They may also develop a walk-through schedule with their leadership team and keep track of the improvements of where they visited.
- Principals must begin with establishing a common vision and expectations for all teachers. This will provide all teachers with consistent, concrete elements to focus on when developing lessons.
- Teachers must grow professionally. They must attend at least one seminar, training, workshop, or conference that is aligned with their major. They may also try to read books or engage in professional learning networks such as in the social media which is a pathway of ideas, strategies, feedback, resources, and support that every educator should take advantage of in the digital age.
- For future research, the study may be conducted in the regional level or higher and involve a larger sample size. Experimental research design may also be employed to further determine the effect teachers' participation on pupils' learning outcomes.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individuals respondents included in the study.

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